

Real-Time Virtual Jewellery Try-On System Using Augmented Reality

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Abstract—This seminar intends to explore augmented reality to demonstrate how virtual jewellery demonstration can be realised on self imaged mode and captured using webcam. In online jewellery shopping, users will have the opportunity to try-on virtual pieces of jewellery with fully immersive and interactive enhanced experience.

Keywords— Face detection and recognition, Numpy, OpenCV, Pillow

I. INTRODUCTION

A technology known as augmented reality (AR) projects digital data, such text or 3D models, onto the physical world in real-time. The jewellery business is progressively utilising augmented reality (AR) technology to improve the client buying experience. Customers will have a more immersive and interactive buying experience with AR because they can virtually try on jewellery without really wearing it. Customers can interact with virtual 3D models of jewellery using augmented reality (AR), which can be placed onto a live video stream of the customer's face or body. Customers are able to do this before making a purchase to view how a certain piece of jewellery will appear on them.

In this system, faces are found in real-time video captured by a camera using computer vision techniques, and the faces are then decorated with virtual jewellery. The technique starts by taking a frame from the video stream and scaling it appropriately. After that, faces in the frame are found and their facial landmarks are obtained using the face_recognition library. The size of the virtual jewellery piece to be placed is calculated using the facial landmarks, specifically the width and location of the chin. Overall, this system shows how to leverage computer vision libraries and techniques to do image scaling, thresholding, masking, and superimposition to construct an application that adds digital jewellery to live video broadcasts.

The main components of the system are OpenCV computer vision library, Face_recognition library, Numpy, dlib and Pil (Python imaging library).

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The topic of adding virtual accessories to facial images has been widely explored in recent years.

Shridhar S. Kini and Suganya Raman's "Ornament Dressing Room: A Virtual Dressing Room For Jewellery" was published in 2015[1]. This paper outlines a method for locating the control points needed to virtually place the jewellery on the neck.

In order to test out the suggested system, a user must face a Kinect Sensor and the system will augment the jewellery around the user's neck. The suggested solution uses Microsoft Kinect's Depth stream and RGB streams to determine the necessary control point. The technology will undoubtedly shorten the time each piece of jewellery needs to be worn and removed while also improving the user experience.

By Er. Revati Mukesh Raspayle and Prof. Kavita Kelkar, "Towards a Development of Augmented Reality for Jewellery App" was published in 2016[2]. This paper presents an idea that uses a webcam as an input to automatically recognise human faces and tries to glue the desired accessories (such as jewellery or eyeglasses) on them while displaying it on the screen in augmented reality (AR). When a person enters the field of view of the camera, the camera begins detecting that person's face, and the algorithm of the system begins tracking that person's face in order to recognise different facial features. The item will then be immediately applied to that specific face (or body) part whenever the person chooses an item from the shopping list. By using this method, choosing the accessories in a virtual display is much faster. To do this, we employ the HAAR method, which assumes control of the face detection process and merges the accessories. Here, the joints and coordinate positions are used to merge the jewellery. As a result, the accessories are consequently parallel transformed and automatically positioned to the identified human face.

Gaurav Salunke's "Virtual Jewellery Shopping Using Augmented Reality" was published in 2020[3]. The 3D projection of the object for user inspection before to trial in this

system uses the ICP algorithm. The markers are established and the customer's face is detected using the HAAR algorithm. The consumer can use the programme and view how they appear by entering an image of themselves as they would appear if they were standing in front of a screen. The technology will thereby assist the customer in making the best purchase decision. Webcams are used to accomplish this. As soon as a customer chooses an item from an application, the system will detect and track their movements. The chosen item will then automatically adjust to the customer's relevant face portion, allowing the customer to try on various ornaments and determine whether or not they are a good fit for them.

"Jewellery Try on using AR" by Jai Prajapat, Manish Sathe, Simran Shah, and Chinmay Raut (2022)[4]. The user first reaches the user interface of the Jewellery Try on app, which has a button that reads, "Select hand jewellery with some recommendations to improve user experience." The user then chooses the jewellery for the hand depending on their preferences, and the device camera is switched on. This is followed by the Jewellery dataset phase. The Mediapipe dependencies will load once everything has been properly set up, opened, and the hand detection process has been carried out. It records 21 hand landmarks and uses mediapipe encoding methods to encode the spots that were found. Using encoded key points, the chosen jewellery will now be enhanced on the discovered hand. The proposed implementation titled virtual jewellery try-on is a developing technology that is useful for the future generation which has many applications.

III. IMPLEMENTATION

This system detects faces in a webcam-generated video stream using computer vision and image processing techniques and overlays jewellery on the detected face's chin region. This system employs the face_recognition library to find facial landmarks and the OpenCV library to process images and videos. Python's NumPy library is utilised for numerical calculation, and the PIL (Python Imaging Library) module is used for picture editing.

Steps:

- 1) Importing the necessary libraries
 - The cv2 library from OpenCV is used for computer vision tasks.
 - PIL: Python Imaging Library for image processing;
 - numpy: Library for scientific computing with Python;
 - face_recognition: A library for face identification and recognition
- 2) Using the cv2.imread() function of OpenCV to load an image of a piece of jewellery and saving it in the variable jewel_img.
- 3) Starting the camera with the cv2.VideoCapture() function of OpenCV, which retrieves frames from the camera as NumPy arrays
- 4) Executing an infinite loop to continuously take pictures and edit them.
- 5) Using cap.read(), which provides a boolean result and the frame, to read the following frame from the camera. The boolean value of False indicates that the frame and loop couldn't be captured.
- 6) Resize the frame using OpenCV's cv2.resize() method to a dimension of 432x576 pixels.
- 7) Finding faces in the resized frame by using the face_recognition.face_landmarks() function, which provides a list of dictionaries with facial landmarks (such as the eyes, nose, mouth, and chin) for each found face.
- 8) The programme performs the following actions for each face it recognises in the frame:
 - Takes the landmarks for the chin out of the facial landmarks dictionary.
 - Determines the starting point's x and y coordinates for the jewellery picture to be inserted. For the x and y coordinates, respectively, the third and fifth points of the landmark of the chin are used. Based on the distance between the third and fourteenth points of the chin landmark, determines the width and height of the jewellery image. 1.02 times the width is the height's default value.
 - Resizes the jewellery image with OpenCV's cv2.resize() method to match the calculated dimensions.
 - Uses OpenCV's cv2.cvtColor() method to convert the resized jewellery image to grayscale. Creates a binary mask of the jewellery image using OpenCV's cv2.threshold() function. This function sets all pixels with intensity above a threshold to 255 (white) and all other pixels to 0 (black). The threshold value of 230 was chosen through experimentation.
 - Utilises NumPy's boolean indexing to apply the binary mask to the jewellery image. All pixels outside of the jewellery are effectively made transparent as a result.
 - Using the calculated x and y coordinates as well as the width and height of the jewellery image, it extracts the portion of the frame where the jewellery is to be positioned.
 - Utilising the cv2.bitwise_and() function of OpenCV, the binary mask is applied to this region of the frame.
 - Uses OpenCV's cv2.add() function to add the masked jewellery picture to the frame's masked region.
 - Inserts the final image in the region of the frame where the jewellery is to be displayed.

- 9) Employs OpenCV's cv2.cvtColor() method to translate the final frame from the BGR colour space (used by OpenCV) to the RGB colour space (used by PIL).
- 10) Using Image.fromarray(), creates a PIL Image object from the RGB frame.
- 11) Uses the show() function to display the PIL Image object.
- 12) Utilising the numpy.array() function of NumPy and the cv2.cvtColor() function of OpenCV, the PIL Image object is converted back to a NumPy array in the BGR colour space.
- 13) OpenCV is used to display the finished image in window.

IV. RESULT

Using their webcam, users can try on virtual jewellery with the help of this Python software for a virtual try-on system. The script makes use of a number of libraries, including PIL (Python Imaging Library), OpenCV, and face_recognition. The first thing the system does is load an image of the jewellery that will be overlaid over the user's image. Following the initialization of the webcam with OpenCV, a loop that records images from the camera is started. The script makes use of the face_recognition library for each frame to find any faces present in the photo and obtain their facial landmarks. The size of the area where the jewellery will be placed is then determined by extracting the location of the chin and using the distance between the two corners of the jawline.

The script then applies a threshold to the jewellery image to generate a binary mask for the item after resizing it to match the calculated area. After removing any backdrop from the original jewellery image using this mask, the jewellery is then overlaid on the captured frame. In order to display the frame in a window, the script next converts the PIL image object to a NumPy array using OpenCV. Using their webcam, the user can move their head and jewellery till they are in the appropriate position. Overall, this code shows a straightforward but efficient method for developing a virtual try-on system using image processing and computer vision techniques.

Fig 1: shows result of the system

Fig 1: Virtual try of necklace

V. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the virtual jewellery try-on system demonstrated in this system, which uses computer vision techniques, is a creative approach for the jewellery retail sector. The technology precisely determines the position and orientation of the user's face using face identification and landmark detection techniques before superimposing the chosen jewellery on their image in real time. The user can then decide whether to buy the jewellery after seeing how it looks on them. The system is simple to use and offers clients a fun and interactive shopping experience. In the retail jewellery sector, as well as integrate it with online jewellery sales.

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